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Estimates of C input rates using LUCAS data for European grasslands

ABSTRACT

This report is an extension of Deliverable 4.4. to improve the spatial coverage of plant carbon (C) inputs of European grasslands. Currently, there is not enough data from long-term experiments from some regions of Europe including Eastern Europe, Scandinavia and the Mediterranean. Consequently, estimates of plant C input values for grasslands were undertaken using the LUCAS dataset. Plant C inputs vary significantly and the differences in simulated values provides us with an indication of the spatial variation. The effects of management and land use change cannot be determined from the LUCAS data. Future research is required to better understand these and other factors which influence C inputs.

WP4. Grassland management

DELIVERABLE - WP4.5. Estimates of C input rates using LUCAS data for European grasslands

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1. Introduction

The WP4 dataset on grassland LTE was the foundational data which was collected to evaluate the potential for soil C sequestration of European grasslands. Because of the specific requirements to undertake RothC simulations there were many grassland studies which we were not able to utilise. Consequently, the number of data records in the LTE dataset was smaller than optimal and also it did not cover very well many regions of Europe.

It was in this context that we evaluated alternative methods and datasets. This included the LUCAS dataset, ORCHIDEE simulated NPP outputs and MODIS NPP. Previous work by Chang et al. (2021) have shown the potential of ORCHIDEE to estimate C within grasslands at a global scale.

2. Results

Using the RothC simulation methodology described in Del. 4.2. the LUCAS data (2009, 2015 and 2018) we estimated the plant C inputs for European grasslands. The mean plant C inputs were 6.82 t C ha^{-1} (standard error = 0.16). Table 1 lists the mean plant C inputs for each European country according to a simulation which used 2009 as the base year and 2018 as the final year.

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Table 1. The mean and standard error of the mean and standard error (SE) of the simulated plant C inputs (t C ha) for different European countries from grassland using the LUCAS dataset

Country	n	Mean Plant C Input (t C ha ⁻¹)	SE Plant C Inputs (t C ha ⁻¹)
Austria	44	8.1	0.90
Belgium	5	7.1	2.54
Bulgaria	28	6.6	0.89
Czech Republic	60	5.4	0.40
Denmark	2	2.9	2.64
Estonia	12	4.7	0.93
Finland	1	3.0	NA
France	306	7.6	0.31
Germany	109	8.2	0.42
Greece	8	5.1	0.75
Hungary	17	4.0	0.88
Ireland	26	8.7	1.35
Italy	38	6.4	0.66
Latvia	20	4.0	0.67
Lithuania	38	4.7	0.50
Netherlands	9	8.7	1.51
Poland	68	4.2	0.36
Portugal	8	3.2	0.75
Romania	86	6.2	0.57
Slovakia	22	5.2	0.89
Slovenia	18	9.0	1.46
Spain	57	7.8	1.01
Sweden	26	6.6	0.82
UK	53	7.6	0.85

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The simulated plant C inputs are compared with environmental and physical driving factors (rainfall, temperature and clay %) are plotted with the simulated plant carbon inputs (Figures 1 to 4). A map of Europe provides a spatial representation of the location of LUCAS sites which were simulated for plant C inputs (Figure 5).

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Figure 1. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and annual mean rainfall (mm) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

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Figure 2. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C /ha/ yr) values and annual mean temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to different European countries)

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Figure 3. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and annual mean evaporation (mm) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to different European countries)

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Figure 4. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and mean clay content (%) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to different European countries)

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Figure 5. Simulated mean plant carbon input (t C /ha/ yr) values for grassland sites across Europe (derived from the LUCAS dataset)

3. Discussion

The simulation of plant C inputs provides a greater geographic coverage and spatial scale than the estimates from the long-term experiments (D. 4.4.). A drawback of the LUCAS data is the lack of associated meta-data (e.g. management) which could help to explain the variability of the C inputs. A basic comparison of the plant C inputs with rainfall, temperature and evaporation did not show any clear relationships (Figures 1-3). Likewise, there was no clear pattern observed between plant C inputs and the clay % (Figure 4). In contrast to this study, De Rosa et al. (2024) found that sites with a low initial SOC content and high clay content had a positive influence on the change in SOC. While locations with a mean annual temperature $<13^{\circ}\text{C}$ and annual rainfall >700 mm had a positive influence on SOC. De Rosa et al. reported there was increase in SOC stocks of 1.2 t C ha^{-1} which is slightly greater than $1.3 \text{ t C ha year}^{-1}$ which was calculated in this study (between 2009 and 2018). While De Rosa et al. (2024) have demonstrated how LUCAS data can be related to different factors which influence the SOC stocks for grasslands across Europe. Using data from this study we compare the simulated plant C inputs with the annual change in C stock (t C/ ha / yr , from 2009 to 2018) and this shows a strongly positive relationship (Figure 6). In addition, a positive relationship between simulated plant C inputs and the C stock in 2018 (t C/ ha) is given in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and the annual C stock change (t C/ha/yr) for grassland sites across Europe (derived from the LUCAS dataset)

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Figure 7. Simulated mean plant carbon input (t C /ha/ yr) values and the C stock in 2018 (t C/ ha/ yr) for grassland sites across Europe (derived from the LUCAS dataset)

3. 1. Spatial coverage and variability in plant carbon inputs

The spatial coverage of the grassland sites from the LUCAS dataset (Figure 5) is greater than the LTE dataset (Deliverable 4.1.), however there were still parts of Europe with few LUCAS sites. For example, much of Scandinavia was sparsely represented; with just one site in Finland and two sites in Denmark. Similarly, there were few sites in Southern Europe and the Mediterranean region.

There was a large degree of variability in the estimates of plant C inputs. The number of LUCAS sites which were considered acceptable was 1022 and the mean for these data was 6.84 (t C/ ha) and the standard deviation was 5.23. These results indicate that there is a general positive relationship between plant C inputs and both the changes in C stocks and the soil C stock values (Figures 6 and 7), however it is not a very clear or specific relationship. Further work is required to quantify the driving soil, management and environmental factors which control both the plant C inputs and the soil C stocks.

The simulation of plant C inputs are always associated with a level of uncertainty. In the case of the LUCAS data there is an issue with the calculation of SOC stocks which is based on using a pedotransfer function for estimates of bulk density (Hollis et al., 2012). In the 2018 sampling of LUCAS bulk density was determined at selected sites. These data have enabled a soil bulk density map of Europe to be created (Panagos et al., 2024). Future work is now

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possible to use measured bulk density and to evaluate the suitability of using a pedotransfer function.

The lack of meta-data associated with LUCAS data is problematic to confirm/ validate the land use at each LUCAS site. Previous work has been undertaken to verify the land use at each LUCAS site (d'Andrimont et al., 2022), however there remains some uncertainty regarding temporary grassland in the years in between when LUCAS sites were sampled. Moreover, there is no management information to classify the LUCAS sites according to practices such as nutrient inputs which can significantly effect both plant C inputs and the changes in C stocks.

3. 2. Areas of future research

New methods

Currently some inter-disciplinary research being undertaken which brings together soil science, remote sensing, modelling and plant science. A current example is the Dutch research project “An EO framework for soil Carbon Sequestration Monitoring” (<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/608ee7ac0cbb450993f9bf0ddcc98089>) which seeks to utilise remote sensing (RS) data to monitor the carbon sequestration of agricultural soils for the Netherlands. This is a challenging attempt to capture the effects of land use and management at a large spatial scale using readily available data from satellites. The success of this type of approach is yet to be confirmed as there are significant issues with the validation/ calibration of the RS data as well as coping with the dynamics of the weather within a complex systems.

The utilisation of long-term Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Net Primary Production (NPP) data has been shown to evaluate carbon uptake by grasslands (Sha et al., 2020). Further development of applying such remote sensing data shows promising potential to assess grassland C sequestration at a regional scale. A good example of national scale mapping of soil C sequestration potential was undertaken in Denmark (Gutierrez et al., 2023). The method applied by Gutierrez et al. involved RothC simulations at a 1 km spatial resolution with 2018 LUCAS data as the input data. This approach is probably fine for arable land which accounts for most of the agricultural area in Denmark, however it is unlikely to be able produce acceptable simulations for grassland. In this study we were able to identify only two LUCAS sites which were appropriate grassland sites.

There is currently interest in the area of data harmonisation in Europe. Froger et al. (2024) compared data from multiple EU national network countries and from LUCAS. This study by Froger et al. highlights that there is high variability between national network and LUCAS data. Plus, there are differences in the sampling strategy and consequently there are

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different results from each. This is an important on-going issue which is especially important for grassland as there was a lack of sample intensity to properly evaluate soils at a broad spatial scale (Froger et al., 2024).

All existing and new methods are constrained and limited by the lack of suitable sites with long-term soil C data. Firstly, the provision of quality data is essential to undertake valid modelling simulations with RothC or with another model. Second, it is important that robust data is available to monitor and validate any future modelling results. A framework for MRV (measurement/monitoring, reporting and verification) was outlined by Smith et al. (2020) and this called for the establishment of benchmark sites with representative land cover/land-use type and soil types. Unfortunately, there exists a lack of benchmark sites representing grassland in Europe. Without greater spatial coverage across Europe it will be difficult to map soil C sequestration potential with an high level of confidence in all regions. Inevitably, in some parts of Europe such as in Germany and the UK (where there is more data available) it is more feasible to determine the soil C sequestration potential.

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